

MASS MARKET MODERNISM: COMIC STRIPS AND THE CULTURE OF CONSUMPTION

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In 1988 Kirk Varnedoe, a curator at the Museum of Modern Art in New York, noted that 'the founding premise of Modernism was to call into question the distinction between high and low art'.¹ Varnedoe's observation provided the organising principle for his and Adam Gopnik's 1990 exhibition and book, *High & Low: Modern Art and Popular Culture*. The book and exhibition subvert established hierarchies of art by re-examining the relationship between 'highbrow' and 'lowbrow' artistic pursuits at the turn of this century. In their examination, the two curators marshal the usual suspects. The 'highbrow' contenders are modern art masters, such as Picasso, Braque, Gris, and Leger, and in the 'lowbrow' corner we find mass circulated newspapers, graffiti, and advertising. But into this pack of hardened Modernist veterans Varnedoe and Gopnik throw a joker, comic strips. The two regard comic strips as 'another kind of modern art' and a form that shared modern art's common desire to establish a 'new universal language of art'.²

For historians interested in the transformation of American society between 1880 and 1920, Varnedoe and Gopnik's conception of comic art as a language suggests fresh ways of using Modernism and modernisation as explanatory concepts. To be sure, Varnedoe and Gopnik's interest is in the hermeneutics of Modernism and not American history, but their work parallels historical work on modernisation, Modernism, representation, and the establishment of cultural hierarchies along 'highbrow/lowbrow' divisions. In recent years historians have delineated the transformative force of modernisation that entailed: the development of new technologies and modes of transportation and communication that resulted in large scale industrial production and craft deskilling; the emergence of national markets and advertising; and the growth of urban centres whose populations had sufficient income to participate in a new leisure economy.³ At the same time scholars have grappled with Modernism, describing it variously as:

a holistic 'culture that seeks to know reality' whilst recognising that such efforts will always be incomplete;

rejecting Victorian values such as 'a moral creed based on repression and rationalism';

a sensibility 'often rooted in hostility to modernization'; and

a cultural form that only existed in the United States as a machine aesthetic.⁴

On occasion these analytical strands have come together, perhaps most successfully, in Richard Wrightman Fox and T.J. Jackson Lears's edited collection of essays, *The Culture of Consumption*. In that volume Jackson Lears, Christopher Wilson, and Jean-Christophe Agnew demonstrate how the ambivalence of a Modernist sensibility undermined attempts at a critical stand against effects of modernisation such as the commodification of society. Specifically Lears and his fellow contributors regard the modern condition as a weightlessness brought on by the erosion of a moral creed and the 'corrosive impact of the market on familiar values'. Into this void stepped the entrepreneurs of mass market amusements, and advertisers, who offered visceral, if illusionary, sensations under the banner of 'real life'. In this ethereal world, where advertising became an all pervasive if slippery language, Agnew holds that consumers adopted a strategy of 'acquisitive cognition' in which commodities were acquired not simply through purchase 'but through a kind of all-pervasive knowingness, a thoroughgoing acquaintance with commodities' actual and imagined attributes'. Yet even this approach failed to provide a solid foundation since it reproduced 'the dislocating dynamic it was intended to reduce because the attributes' constantly changed. Although Agnew limits himself to discussing the appearance of such an 'acquisitive cognition' in the work of Henry James, his concept can be applied to the language of comic strips.⁵

The relationship between comic strips and Modernism can be understood through two approaches. First, comics can be seen as a response to the process of modernisation and second as a humour based response to the problems of representation faced by a society in transition. As a response to modernisation, comic strips appear as a social phenomenon, in this case as one of the first widely-consumed commodities produced by the emerging mass entertainment industry. Such an approach helps us locate comic strips within an historical framework but it is still necessary to describe how comics came to, and could, articulate Modernism. The comic strip mode of representation, particularly the use of sequential panels and narratives without closure, pre-dated bolder Modernist efforts to reconfigure strategies of representation. In his proposal to read art as codes of social recognition that come together as signs, art theorist Norman Bryson argues that artists can transfigure existing conventions and project new understandings into social discourse through the act of creation. That is, visual representations are not simply metonymical forms but language that can both transform and reflect a culture. Daniel Bell may contest that there was no Modernist culture in turn-of-the-century America, save that of the impersonal machine aesthetic, but comic strips gave the machine product a personality and covered the nation by 1908. Comic strips were representations

through which an increasingly commodified society saw and constituted itself. In short, comic strips helped create Modernism in both its formal art meaning and its broader cultural denotation. My account of the commodification of comic art is an effort to show the manner in which cultures are transformed by examining the role of one form in creating a Modernist American culture.⁶

From Humour Journals to Mass Market Modernism

The Modernism that comic strips delivered to the nation in the early years of the twentieth century initially took shape in the pages of *Puck*, *Life*, *Judge* and numerous other illustrated humour journals.⁷ Begun in 1876, *Puck* was the first American illustrated humour magazine published on a regular basis. It demonstrated both the influence of European antecedents and the special, and distinctively American, culture of New York City. The graphic material it published drew its form and technique from European traditions, but except for the occasional nod to the German artist Wilhelm Busch, its content was locally inspired by an emerging culture of the cities that the humour magazines not only celebrated but helped create. *Puck* defined a format for American illustrated humour magazines followed by its main competitors, *Judge* and *Life*.⁸

Illustrated humour magazines like *Puck* fused the rough and tumble urban political culture of Gilded Age America with the rich pageant of public entertainment that filled up the leisure hours of thousands of men and women. The journals were but part of a vast cultural industry created by entrepreneurs and consumers of professional sport, circuses, minstrel shows, vaudeville, theatre, amusement parks, dime novels, and other cheap literature that helped mediate class and ethnic identities. For instance, the 20 October 1892 issue of *Life* contained a graphic entitled 'The Advantages of An Extensive Repertoire' by Franklin Morris Howarth, a New York artist of Philadelphia origins. In seven unframed scenes, this piece depicted the attempts of a street musician to appease the cop walking the beat. The musician commenced his performance with 'The Star Spangled Banner'. Howarth probably wanted readers to assume that the cop lost in contemplation in the background would not interfere with this display of American patriotism. The joke plays out when the cop demonstrates his intention to put a stop to the performance. The resourceful musician switches to the anthems of Germany, and England, before striking the right note with an Irish song.

A hundred years later the Irish cop joke appears stale. But the piece contained more than a stereotypical joke; it offered a vision, shared by artist and reader, of power in the American city. The rapid shift to German, English, and finally Irish

music demonstrates the musician's — and Howarth's — knowledge of urban America. Power, in this case the ability to make, break, and enforce the law, did not belong exclusively to those who regarded themselves as 'American'. It also belonged to German-Americans, Anglo-Americans, and Irish-Americans. But as Howarth suggested, one could never be sure to whom it belonged on any given street corner. The musician had to shape his identity in response to his audience, an audience composed of both immigrant and native-born Americans.

Magazines like *Puck*, *Life*, and *Judge* acquainted readers with a new urban political and leisure culture. But through graphics like Howarth's 'Advantages of an Extensive Repertoire', they simultaneously acquainted those readers with a new art form, a new way of seeing themselves. Howarth was an important figure in the development of the comic strip. For instance, his placement of text, in the form of 'music' emanating from the performer's trumpet, as a component element of the graphic was one of the first instances in American narrative comic humour where text and graphic were combined in a representation. Howarth's use of this important feature of comic strips placed him in the forefront of a movement that adapted and expanded Rodolphe Töpffer's and Busch's format for an American audience. Like those two European artists, Howarth narrowed the distance between the textual and the visual to create a comic art form that increased the emphasis on character and narrative by embedding them in the graphic image itself.

Howarth was one of a number of American comic artists who captured an urban vision by yoking narrative humour with graphic illustration. Other artists used a narrative structure in caricatures of city faces and types to comment on the metropolitan scene. For instance, 'What Will Become of The Men Who Stay Out Late' transformed a dude out for an evening on the town into an owl. Other illustrations depicted the expressions of an electric car motorman during a day's work, and those of a man who receives the news, by phone, that his mother-in-law has cut short her visit and left while he was at work. Variations on these types of illustration included a man who turned into a pig by eating at a lunch counter, a lover's quarrel illustrated solely by feet, and 'Puck's Easy Lessons in Caricature', which demonstrated how to depict any type of face by adding to a basic oval shape. 'The Transformation of a Paying Teller', in which a teller transformed from a humble servant into an outraged bureaucrat because a customer had endorsed a check at the wrong end, demonstrated the narrative possibilities of these types of illustrations.⁹

These artists' use of narrative form and comic art technique allowed them to create new possibilities for comic characters. For instance, rather than illustrate one

or two line gags, straight out of vaudeville, Howarth presented unfolding stories through a series of panels. But, like vaudeville, these illustrations worked familiar narrative genres where the joke lay in the novel solution to a stock situation. Stock situations and types were the mainstay of comic art. The most important of these pictorial representations of urban social types in the development of American comic strips was the naughty boy originally borrowed from Busch's *Max und Moritz*. Howarth, Michael Angelo Woolf, Frank Bellow, and numerous other artists filled the pages of illustrated humour journals with cartoons featuring the antics of rough-hewn city kids. These depictions of children were seemingly the antithesis of the innocent Victorian child. The first comic strip character, the Yellow Kid, was developed from the urban naughty kid type.

The illustrated humour that appeared in *Puck*, *Life*, and *Judge* paved the way for the comic strip. What separated this early American illustrated humour from the comic strip was the lack of a cast of continuing characters or character, the regular use of word balloons, a format that required weekly or daily appearances by these characters in a named strip, and a place in a mass circulated medium, which made the form and characters consumer staples. In 1883, Joseph Pulitzer commenced publication of a Sunday edition of his newly acquired newspaper, the *New York World*. The *World* carried detailed stories about the infamous side of city life, stories that helped shape gossip, rumour, and scandal into a new, marketable genre: the news. In short, Pulitzer, building on the dubious achievements of the penny press, created in the urban culture of New York City one of the first units of what we now call the mass media. One of the *World's* important innovations was the introduction of illustrations to accompany reports of the news. Another was the regular use of editorial cartoons.

In 1889 the *World* capitalised on its successful use of illustrated material with the publication of a one-page illustrated humour section, 'The World's Funny Side', in its Sunday edition. This section had a similar appearance to the humour magazines except it had no colour plates. In 1894 the *World* acquired a colour press and began a Sunday colour supplement. The first comic strip character to enjoy widespread popularity, Richard Outcault's Yellow Kid, appeared as an unnamed figure in a series of illustrations in Pulitzer's Sunday *World* in 1895 and 1896. Outcault's main contribution to the development of the comic strip was that he crystallised a succession of urban kid types into a single character, the Yellow Kid. Between 1895 and 1896, Outcault's Yellow Kid defined the artistic and commercial dimensions of comic strips.

On 5 May 1895, the *World* published Outcault's 'At the Circus in Hogan's

Alley'. The illustration depicted a group of city children performing acrobatics. It was the first of a series of large comic illustrations of city kids that appeared in the *World* under the more or less continuous running title of 'Hogan's Alley'. In following weeks Outcault added text to the feature, first in the form of placards and billboards, and then on the front of the nightshirt of one of the kids. Dubbed 'The Yellow Kid' by the newspaper's readers, this figure became the focal point of the strip. In his Hogan's Alley appearances the Kid chronicled the activities of New Yorkers through the eyes of its urchin children. Outcault's mixture of imagery and language showed the city as coarse, boisterous, and full of unexpected pleasures. The Kid 'spoke' a rough city dialect that mingled different class and ethnic tongues. His appearance led many to mistake him for a 'Chinaman' until Outcault named him Mickey Dugan. The Kid's readers made him the centre of a craze in New York and nearby eastern cities. Products of the craze included Yellow Kid buttons, chewing gum, chocolate figurines, cigars, and ladies' fans.¹⁰ The popularity of the Yellow Kid demonstrated that a distinctive comic art character, drawn in an urban setting, could sell newspapers and other products. By the end of 1895, the *Sunday World* circulation averaged half a million copies — almost a 100 per cent increase over the 1891 circulation.¹¹ Outcault, Pulitzer, and his competitor William Randolph Hearst, recognised the commercial possibilities that the popularity of the Yellow Kid and the increased circulation of newspapers offered. The opportunistic Hearst obtained Outcault's services, over the objection of Pulitzer, and in October 1896 launched a comic supplement to his *New York Journal* built around 'The Yellow Kid'.

Between 1896 and 1901 the contributors to the *Journal's* comic supplement Richard Outcault, Rudolph Dirks, Frederick Opper, and others, fashioned the comic strip. Outcault abandoned the Yellow Kid early in 1898, probably because he failed to secure copyright protection for the character and could not control his replication by other artists and advertisers. But the success of Outcault's character prompted other artists to create their own continuing characters and experiment with the form. In particular, Dirks in 'The Katzenjammer Kids', and Opper in 'Happy Hooligan', refined the combination of character, word balloons and panel layout that define modern comic strips. Like Outcault, Dirks and Opper deployed urban types — naughty kids and a hapless Irish immigrant — in their strips. But the popularity of the strips, the increasing commercialisation of American culture, and the growth of national markets gave these and other strips a broader audience than the Yellow Kid ever enjoyed.

Beginning in November 1900, Hearst used the comic strips produced in New

York in his other papers such as the San Francisco *Examiner*. In 1902, Hearst further offset his heavy costs for comic strips by selling them to newspapers around the country. Hearst's actions opened a national market for comic strips. By 1903, newspapers across the country carried comic strip supplements in their Sunday editions. At least forty-eight newspapers in thirty-three locations carried comic strips and by 1908 this figure had grown to at least eighty-three newspapers in fifty locations.¹² This expansion transformed comic strips from a New York phenomenon to a national one and placed comic strip characters and the art form before a wide national audience, laying the basis for their use in other products. It also provided urban and rural readers with a weekly shared experience and brought together diverse national audiences as markets for mass media products. Apart from the healthy increases in circulation that the New York papers experienced when they introduced comic strips, two factors contributed to the rapid spread of the art form in the nation's newspapers: the growth of syndication and the consolidation of control by newspaper chains. Both the *World* and the *Journal* organised syndicates to sell comic strip features to other papers. Independent syndicates, which began to supply feature material to newspapers, particularly Sunday papers in the 1880s, developed their own comic supplements that were sold to papers across the nation. Also, by 1900 eight newspaper chains existed, the largest of which was the nine-paper chain of Edward W. Scripps.¹³ Hearst was a key figure in the development of both syndicated material and newspaper chains. By 1903, the comic art that originated in Hearst papers appeared in at least seventeen papers across the country and Hearst himself owned six papers in four cities. According to Frank Mott, by 1922 'Hearst owned twenty daily papers and eleven Sunday papers in thirteen of the largest American cities'. The consolidation of the production and distribution of comic strips proceeded apace with the centralisation of newspapers, news dissemination, and business and industry in general.¹⁴

Comic strips were a national and not an exclusively urban phenomenon by 1903.¹⁵ Comic strips attracted the interest of newspaper publishers since they helped to increase circulation. The Memphis *Commercial Appeal's* Sunday circulation rose roughly 20 per cent between late 1901 and early 1902 after the introduction of comic strips on 16 March 1902. In Kansas the Topeka *Daily Capital's* Sunday circulation rose 8 per cent between October 1903 and January 1904 after strips commenced on 22 November 1903.¹⁶ These circulation figures also give some idea of the regional circulation of the papers. In 1900, Memphis had a population of 102,320, and Topeka 33,608. Either one in three people in Memphis and one in two people in Topeka bought these papers or a good part of their circulation was outside the city limits. In

1903, most newspapers with comic strips had significant sales outside their census-defined base. The establishment of Rural Free Delivery by the Post Office between 1898 and 1906 boosted urban newspapers' rural circulations. By 1903, newspapers across the country carried comic strips and the circulation of papers with strips rose, suggesting that comics were a popular feature. Moreover, many of these newspapers carried the same comic strips. By 1908, syndicates had brought comic strips to almost the entire nation and established methods of distributing their product that continue to the present. In short, between 1901 and 1908 newspaper publishers and syndicates helped shape the New York phenomenon of comic strips into a shared national cultural artefact.¹⁷

I could offer more evidence of the widespread availability of comic strips — anecdotal tales of their readership, and even some early social science surveys that revealed almost universal readership among children¹⁸ — but none of this information would answer the most telling question: Why did small town and rural audiences find comic strips so appealing? It would be easy to suggest that their appeal lay in their novelty — richly coloured illustrations offering a kinetic view of large city life — but I suspect that this is too easy an answer. In his work on the launching of a commercial culture in New York City, William Taylor suggested that the success of the Yellow Kid came about due to its open-ended humour, which gave it 'comic significance to those approaching it from different social perspectives'.¹⁹ But that strip only appeared in New York City newspapers and its circulation was never national. When newspapers across the nation began to carry comic strips, artists created works that were less urban in their content than the strips that appeared in New York papers in the late 1890s. Artists attempted to straddle the urban/rural diversity of American society and embellish their characters with even broader qualities than those that appealed to a diverse city audience. Artists toned down the ethnic jests and dialogue gags that underpinned many of the early strips. Syndicates tended to limit the distribution of comic strips premised on ethnic humour, such as 'Abie the Agent', to larger cities. Manoeuvres of that kind suggest that any sense of an American culture created by comic strips was still fragile and open to challenge from humorous depictions of the diversity of that society. By 1903, among the best known and widely distributed strips, only 'Happy Hooligan' was clearly set in a city. 'The Katzenjammer Kids' had a semi-rural setting and eventually moved to a tropical island. Artists set other popular strips, such as 'Buster Brown' and 'Sambo and His Funny Noises', which began in 1902 and 1904 respectively, in urban/rural crossroads.

Comics as Commodity and Agent of Change: Buster Brown

A study of the Buster Brown comic strips reveals the amalgam of interests and techniques that extended comics' Modernist vision to the nation. Richard Outcault created Buster Brown after his failure to ensure copyright protection of the Yellow Kid. Outcault created the character with the intention to license Buster's likeness to other products. Buster Brown's physical appearance, and manner of dress, replicated Victorian representations of childhood innocence. As a visual type he could be described as a Little Lord Fauntleroy. In determining Buster's depiction Outcault hit on the image of a child familiar to many Americans. Commercial lithographers, such as Currier and Ives, and nineteenth-century periodicals like *Godeys' Ladies Book*, made the innocent child a visual staple in the United States. Moreover, the Victorian child appeared on thousands of trade cards, a promotion device, used by diverse enterprises such as large-scale manufacturers and small-town dry goods stores. On to this Victorian icon, Outcault layered comic art's urban naughty child themes. Outcault created a comic strip with diverse appeal by combining two visions of childhood. But he did so employing the formal attributes of comic strips — sequential panels, continuing characters, and word balloons.²⁰

'Buster Brown' first appeared in the *New York Herald* on 4 May 1902. Buster Brown was a mischievous young boy from a middle-class family who played practical jokes. Buster's jokes often back-fired. Consequently, he resolved at the end of every Sunday strip to improve his ways or at least learn a lesson from his mistake. The next week he would be back at his old tricks. Outcault repeated this basic premise in new stories week after week. The strip's humour derived in part from Buster's inability to keep his resolve. The skill with which Richard Outcault told a new story within the basic framework added to the strip's appeal. The reader had to appreciate the strip's framework and yet repress that knowledge in order to let the story unfold. Those who read the strip regularly understood that Buster's mischievous side was held in check by his practicality. The repetition of the theme assured readers of the containment of this mischief. Like the Yellow Kid before him Buster was a distinct character yet 'he' was simply a pen and ink drawing. Moreover, Buster's characteristics, and copyright status, made him a 'personality' that could be marketed.

One mark of Buster's personality was the resolution at the end of each strip. These aphoristic resolutions became one of the formal narrative devices of the strip. They did not so much close each episode, but, through the expectation of Buster breaking his resolve, posit a beginning for the next episode. Outcault's use of resolutions opened 'Buster Brown' to alternative readings. For instance, during the

1906-1912 campaign against comic strips, Maud Summers, a member of the Playground Association, castigated 'Buster Brown' as deceitful whereas an unsigned editorial in the Christian reform journal, *Outlook*, found the strip to have some redeeming qualities, possibly because Outcault occasionally advocated 'Christian' business practices. The resolution also displayed Outcault's ambiguous concern with the culture he was helping to create. In one resolution, Outcault through Buster stated that 'it must be wicked to go to church on Sunday knowing that you're going to push someone hard for a dollar on Monday'. But these sentiments did not stop Outcault from pushing his product before the public for a dollar. Indeed 'Buster Brown' may have been so marketable precisely because of this 'populist' anti-business sentiment.²¹

By 1908 'Buster Brown' was a nationally-known name that produced considerable revenue for its owner. For instance, Outcault's royalties from a Buster Brown stage show alone came to \$44,000 between 1903 and mid-1907. Outcault sought to make the most of his success. In January 1906, tempted by a lucrative offer, Outcault left the New York *Herald* for Hearst's newspapers. On 21 January 1906, Hearst's New York *American* published its first episode of 'Buster Brown'. As with Outcault's earlier move of the Yellow Kid from the *World* to the *Journal*, the transfer was the subject of legal action over the copyright of the strip. The outcome of the case left the rights to the comic strip title 'Buster Brown' with the New York *Herald*, but gave Outcault license to draw the characters. Another later case established that Outcault owned all other rights to 'Buster Brown'. The *Herald* hired a succession of artists to produce its own version of 'Buster Brown'. At the *American*, Outcault overcame the problem of not being able to name his strip 'Buster Brown' by drawing his characters in the space normally provided for the title. Buster Brown and his dog Tige were so well known, to comic strip readers at least, that Outcault could simply ask 'Guess Who?' to have the text and the images act as a title. In 1908 Buster appeared in twenty-four newspaper across the country. The aggregate circulation of the newspapers carrying 'Buster Brown' equalled only 3 to 4 per cent of the total United States' population, but it is probable that each copy of these papers had multiple readers with perhaps as much as 10 per cent of the population exposed weekly to the comic strip Buster. But Buster's audience extended beyond the pages of the comic strip.²²

Outcault licensed Buster Brown's image to numerous advertisers. Buster Brown was the first comic strip character licensed in such a fashion that it constituted a brand name. Buster's diverse use distinguished him from other illustrated characters, such as Aunt Jemima, Sunny Jim, and Phoebe Snow, whose images

companies established purely as trademark figures for one product and who were not comic strip characters. Buster's celebrity grew out of multi-representations, whereas Sunny Jim and the others were each tied to a single product.²³

In 1904 Outcault set up shop at the St. Louis World's Fair and licensed his character to a wide variety of manufacturers. The licensees included the Brown Shoe Company and Robert Ingersoll, the pioneer of inexpensive watches. Ingersoll, looking for new ways to sell watches, struck on the idea of a Buster Brown Watch to be given away with a pair of Buster Brown shoes. Ingersoll was guaranteed a certain number of sales and the shoe company worked the wholesale price of the watch into the retail price of the shoes. The significance of Ingersoll's marketing scheme was not so much that it used a popular comic strip character to sell a variety of products, but that it linked these products together in such a fashion that the character constituted a brand name. For instance, Ingersoll's first Buster Brown watch carried a direct advertisement for the shoes, but it also acted as an advertisement for the comic strip. Numerous other products, including textiles, harmonicas, a soft drink, coffee, flour, bread, apples, suits, hosiery, and pianos used Buster Brown as a brand name. Buster Brown dolls, toys, and games, reprints of the comic strip, and a touring Buster Brown musical stage show extended the dimensions of Buster's popularity and recognition.²⁴

Advertisers who used Buster Brown sought national recognition and distribution for their products. For instance, Ivan Frank & Co., a child's clothing wholesaler of New York, distributed a promotional pamphlet that described their audience as extending 'from Maine to California'. There are examples of children's clothing advertisements featuring Buster Brown from Rhode Island and Washington state, so Frank & Co. probably made good on their claim. The Buster Brown brand name was so successful that Ivan Frank merged his company with the Chattanooga mill he represented, and formed Buster Brown Textiles Incorporated. This firm, since bought out by Gerber, still operates as Buster Brown Apparel.²⁵

The other major Buster Brown licensee, the Brown Shoe Company of St. Louis, took an advertisement in the *World's Fair Bulletin* of January 1902 proclaiming the US as 'the territory of the Brown Shoe Company'. The ad featured a map showing the territorial gains of the US on which photographs of Brown's salesmen were superimposed according to their territory. The advertisement positioned Brown Shoes as a company with a national vision. After it bought the Buster Brown name for its shoes, the company expanded rapidly. Between 1902 and about 1907 the physical plant of the Brown Shoe Company doubled from four to eight factories. To promote its shoes, the company ran a national series of 'Buster Brown Outdoor

Receptions' featuring a nine-year-old boy dressed to resemble the comic strip character. In 1910, J.H. Sawyer, the advertising manager for the Brown Shoe Company, reported in *Judicious Advertising* that Buster Brown and the touring show secured the company effective advertising, often without cost. The title of Sawyer's article, 'Buster Brown Advertises Shoes', gave clear expression to the character's worth as a trademark.²⁶

Buster Brown was one of the first national name brands with a diverse image that allowed a multiplicity of meanings to be ascribed to it. 'He' united entertainment and consumer goods. Indeed 'Buster Brown' cannot be understood solely as a comic strip. All of his incarnations contributed to the make-up of his character, and each reinforced, or advertised the others. Moreover, this type of advertising, in the form of entertainment and consumption, allowed Buster's audience to expand their contact with the character by purchasing one of his products. Readers of the strip no longer had to wait for Sunday to get a dose of 'Buster Brown'. For instance, a 1908 advertisement for the Buster Brown doll in the Sears Roebuck catalogue described it as 'a very fine imitation of the Buster Brown you read about'. It added 'this doll will be a delight to the children on account of the popularity of Buster Brown'. And, in the same year the *Daily Oklahoman*, an Oklahoma City newspaper that carried the 'Buster Brown' comic strip, contained advertisements for Buster Brown Shoes along with a notice of a live performance by Buster and Tige in a local clothing store. A local bakery ran concurrent advertisements for Buster Brown Bread. In his 1953 autobiography, *Bad Boy*, the crime writer Jim Thompson, who was reared in Oklahoma City at this time, refers to his Buster Brown blouse as a customarily worn item of clothing. In this fashion, through the purchase of a 'Buster Brown' product, a cultural act, reading comic strips, was further tied to acts of consumption and the basis laid for the wholesale selling of a culture of consumption.²⁷

More than a simple use of Buster Brown's likeness and the techniques of comic art linked comic strips and advertising. Some merchants adopted the maxims expressed in Buster's/Outcault's weekly resolution as advertising slogans. For instance in a 4 March 1906 episode from the *American* entitled, 'Buster Brown: His Snowman', the resolution read, in part:

How are you to gain your first idea of a man except by his clothes? They are the key to his nature, breeding and taste. Commence at the bath tub, and nice stockings and shoes boys.

Another later resolution read:

Clothes are more important than most of us think. What else have you to judge a stranger by? ... Flashy attire shows vulgarity. Very gaudy clothes are worn by

*vain, cheap people. Since your clothes are your best advertisement, try to advertise well, then live up to your advertisement ... Don't advertise All Wool and then produce cotton. Don't try to fool 'em. It don't pay.*²⁸

In 1906, Outcault's Chicago-based advertising agency transferred these sentiments into advertisements for W.B. Hutchinson Co., a Seattle clothing store, and a Los Angeles store. A resolution within the advertisement stated 'that if you wish to march along you must be clad in the latest. The better your apparel the swifter will be your progress'.²⁹ In another 1906 strip Outcault expressed his notion of good business practices. The resolution said, '*Business*. What a lot of trickery and treachery is done in thy name. How many so called Christians excuse their meanness by saying "Business is Business." There's lots better ways of being a good Christian than going to church — one way is being honest and generous in business'.³⁰ In a 1913 advertisement for F.E. Ballou, a Providence, Rhode Island clothing store, Outcault's agency adapted this sentiment to read, '*Resolved*. That people make their good luck by doing the right thing. We have made ours by giving our patrons the right kind of goods. Square deal always wins. We want to keep our patrons'.³¹

Outcault's advertising agency prepared the advertisements, which probably accounts for the shared values with the comic strip resolutions. The use of the resolution united advertising and comic strips through the personality of Buster. In these advertisements Buster, an entertainment celebrity, acted as the spokesman for the company. But Buster also served as the brand name for many items. The United States Copyright Office in the Library of Congress has over 10,000 individual copyright registrations for advertisements using Buster Brown created by Outcault's advertising agency. Buster's image mediated the reception of the product and gave them a distinctive, if polysemic, 'personality'. For instance, it is possible that parents bought Buster Brown shoes for their children out of regard for the Christian business practices and responsibilities Outcault advocated. The recipients of the shoes, on the other hand, may have wanted them as a form of identification with Buster's youthful rebellion. '*Buster Brown Plays Cowboy*', published in the *New York Herald* on 30 July 1905, demonstrated the interplay between these two aspects of 'Buster Brown'. In his resolution Buster admits to being wrong in 'picking out things to do' and then states, 'you can't be happy unless you are good'. But this sentiment is undercut by Tige's winking comment, 'a lot of wise talk from a chap who is always slipping'.³²

The structure of Buster Brown's personality made him a figure open to different and simultaneous interpretations that translated into diverse market appeal. Buster Brown showed that a character-based image made a wide range of goods

and services attractive to disparate audiences. In addition to containing the different motivations for consumption, Buster Brown united the provision of different types of goods and services from large-scale manufacturers, such as the Brown Shoe Company, to small shopkeepers, such as F.E. Ballou of Providence. This unification may have helped to contain tensions produced when localised economies were subjected to national market forces. More to the point, Buster's diverse usages represent the gradual transformations that took place as a locally oriented producerist society became a centralised consumer society. Hal Barron, a historian of rural America, recently discovered a seemingly paradoxical use of Buster and Tige in a series of anti-mail-order advertisements run in the upper-Midwest and West in 1916. As Barron notes, Buster was 'a paragon of national mass popular culture' and a familiar figure to local communities through the shoes that 'were sold only by local retailers and were not available by mail order'.³³ In this case Buster Brown literally represented the process of transformation where new cultural forms overlay, interact, and flow out of the culture being displaced. My examination of Buster Brown suggests that the culture formed around these products was neither imposed by manufacturers nor created by the populace out of a desire to participate in a democracy of manufactured goods. Rather, consumer culture was created in a struggle to assign meaning and values, to a variety of products, and to lives changing under their impact.

Singling out Buster Brown as a representative component in the long transition from a traditional producerist society to a modern culture of consumption points to the multifaceted causality that brought on this change. The modern era was not constituted simply by an increased and universal consumption of goods and services, but involved the extension of commodity status to, among other things, ideas and symbols and the development of intellectual property.³⁴ Comic art was one of the subjects, objects, and agents of this change. Comic strips not only transformed comic art; by stretching its commodity value, they also transformed the culture. The simple, repeatable, easily recognisable form of comic strips made a Modernist aesthetic generally available. By the mid-1910s Americans across the country could open their newspapers and see the same strips. They could also buy an array of products branded with the image of one of the most popular comic strip characters. Ill at ease and hesitantly, Americans began to recognise these comic strips and their characters as part of their daily lives. Around such recognitions America became a national culture of consumption.

NOTES

I would like to thank Anthony Ashbolt for his comments on this paper.

- 1 Kirk Varnedoe quoted in 'The Modern Prepares for the Twenty-first Century', *New York Times*, 6 March 1988, section 2, cited in Lawrence W. Levine, *Highbrow/Lowbrow: The Emergence of Cultural Hierarchy in America*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Mass., 1988, p. 247.
- 2 Kirk Varnedoe and Adam Gopnik, *High & Low: Modern Art and Popular Culture*, Museum of Modern Art, New York, 1990, pp. 153-4.
- 3 For changes in the organisation of work and its effect see Roy Rosenzweig, *Eight Hours for What We Will: Workers and Leisure in an Industrial City, 1870-1920*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, Mass., 1983; David Montgomery, *The Fall of the House of Labor*, Cambridge University Press, New York, 1987; Herbert Gutman, *Work, Culture and Society in Industrializing America: Essays in American Working-Class and Social History*, Vintage, New York, 1976. See also Harry Braverman, *Labor and Monopoly Capital: The Degradation of Work in the Twentieth Century*, Monthly Review Press, New York, 1974; and E.P. Thompson, 'Time, Work-Discipline, and Industrial Capitalism', *Past and Present*, no. 38, 1967, pp. 56-97. Works examining the new leisure economy include Lewis A. Erenberg, *Steppin' Out: New York Nightlife and the Transformation of American Culture, 1890-1930*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago, 1981; Daniel Horowitz, *The Morality of Spending: Attitudes Toward the Consumer Society in America, 1875-1940*, Johns Hopkins University Press, Baltimore, 1985; John F. Kasson, *Amusing The Million: Coney Island at the Turn of the Century*, Hill and Wang, New York, 1978; Lawrence W. Levine, *Highbrow/Lowbrow*; Kathy Peiss, *Cheap Amusements: Working Women and Leisure in Turn of the Century New York*, Temple University Press, Philadelphia, 1986. Works that stress the importance of the 1920s in shaping a fully realised Modernist culture include Roland Marchand, *Advertising the American Dream: Making Way for Modernity, 1920-1940*, University of California Press, Berkeley, 1985; Alice Goldfarb Marquis, *Hopes and Ashes: The Birth of Modern Times*, Free Press, New York, 1986; and Jeffrey L. Meikle, *Twentieth Century Limited: Industrial Design in America, 1925-1939*, Temple University Press, Philadelphia, 1979. For overviews of consumer history see Jean-Christophe Agnew, 'Coming Up for Air: Consumer Culture in Historical Perspective', *Intellectual History Newsletter*, vol. 12, 1990, pp. 3-21; Charles McGovern, 'The Emergence of Consumer History', paper presented at the Organization of American Historians Annual Meeting, 1988.
- 4 Daniel Joseph Singal, 'Toward a Definition of American Modernism', *American Quarterly*, vol. 39, no. 1, Spring 1987, p. 16; Steven Watts, 'Walt Disney: Art and Politics in the American Century', *Journal of American History*, vol. 82, no. 1, June 1995, p. 87; Jackson Lears, 'Uneasy Courtship: Modern Art and Modern Advertising', *American Quarterly*, vol. 39, no. 1, Spring 1987, p. 134; and Daniel Bell, 'Modernism Mummified', *American Quarterly*, vol. 39, no. 1, Spring 1987, p. 125.
- 5 Richard Wrightman Fox and T.J. Jackson Lears (eds), *The Culture of Consumption: Critical Essays in American History, 1880-1980*, Pantheon, New York, 1983, pp. xiii, xv.
- 6 Norman Bryson, 'Semiology and Visual Interpretation', in Norman Bryson, Michael Ann Holly and Keith Moxey (eds), *Visual Theory: Painting and Interpretation*, Polity Press, Cambridge, 1991, pp. 69-70; Bell, 'Modernism Mummified', p. 125.
- 7 Other illustrated humour journals included the in-house magazines of a watch manufacturer and a gentlemen's clothing stores. See *The Waterbury*, and *Smith, Gray & Company's Illustrated Monthly*. Both held National Museum of American History — Archives Center #60 (hereafter NMAH #60), Warshaw Collection, Watches box 4, and Men's Clothing box 1 respectively.

- 8 Every issue of *Puck* contained a full-page political cartoon on the cover, a double-page political cartoon in the centre pages, and a full-page social cartoon on the back cover. For details see the entries for each magazine in David E.E. Sloan (ed.), *American Humour Magazines and Comic Periodicals*, Greenwood Press, New York, 1987.
- 9 *Judge*, vol. 29, 13 July 1895, p. 21; *Judge*, vol. 23, 24 September 1892, p. 199; *Judge*, vol. 23, 20 August 1892, p. 120; *Life*, vol. 20, 20 October 1892, p. 218; *Judge*, vol. 22, 2 April 1892, p. 223; *Puck*, vol. 34, 25 July 1894, p. 358; *Puck*, vol. 28, 26 November 1890, p. 213.
- 10 The Warshaw Collection of Business Americana, NMAH-AC #60, contains a number of advertisements for these products. See also two collector's newsletters, *The Yellow Kid Notes* and *The R.F. Outcault Reader* for details of Yellow Kid products.
- 11 *New York World*, 6 December 1895, p. 1.
- 12 My figures here are drawn from a study of the Library of Congress's holdings, which represent only 7 per cent of daily newspapers published at this time. I estimate that at least 30 per cent of the population had access to comic strips in 1903. My figures for newspapers that carried comic strips in 1903 are derived from a study of 152 daily newspapers, covering 121 locations, in what are now the 48 contiguous states and the District of Columbia. In 1900 there were 2,190 daily papers in America, See Alfred McClung Lee, *The Daily Newspaper in America*, Macmillan, New York, 1937, p. 580. The Library of Congress holds only 339 papers for 1900. The Library only holds 272 papers for 1903, many of which were not daily newspapers. My figures then represent only a sampling. The sample is biased in favour of papers from urban centres and larger towns since these are the papers most often microfilmed and collected by the Library.
- 13 The *Sunday World's* circulation increased from 266,000 in 1893 to 450,000 in 1896. See the *World*, 6 December 1895. Frank Luther Mott, *American Journalism: A History of Newspapers in the United States Through 250 Years, 1690-1940*, Macmillan, New York, 1941, p. 648.
- 14 Mott, *American Journalism*, p. 646.
- 15 Quantifying the readership of early American comic strips is a difficult task. The first comprehensive survey of comic strip readership was taken in the 1930s. Circulation figures for most of the newspapers I examined are available for this period but these only give an indication of the number of copies sold; the figures are not a reliable guide to the market for comic strips. I have therefore concentrated on the potential audience for the comics. I refer to this audience as the 'market'. That is, the population of cities and towns in which comic strips were published. I derived the population figure by adding the 1900 census populations of all incorporated places that my survey showed had newspapers that published comic strips. My figures are on the conservative side because they do not take into account significant populations in surrounding regions for cities such as New York, Chicago, Boston, Minneapolis, and San Francisco. The *Memphis Commercial Appeal* of 1 December 1901 gave details of the paper's extensive distribution in Alabama, Arkansas, Kentucky, Mississippi, and Tennessee. The population of locations with comic strips ranged from 3,437,202 (New York) to 9,453 (Anaconda, Montana). Of the thirty-two locations with comic strips, five were not among the one hundred largest cities in the US. Census figures from *World Almanac*, Press Publishing Co., New York, 1908, pp. 635-37.
- 16 Circulation figures from *Commercial Appeal*, 27 July 1902 — from 29,475 in 1901 to 35,292 in 1902; and *Topeka Daily Capital*, 11 November 1903 and 16 February 1904 — from 15,500 in October 1903 to 16,741 in January 1904. In the absence of any other notable change in the two newspapers it seems that comic strips were primarily responsible for these circulation increases.
- 17 Daniel Boorstin, *The Americans: The Democratic Experience*, Random House, New York,

- 1973, p. 132. Wide circulations were not limited to newspapers with comic strips. The Rochester *Democrat & Chronicle* of 9 November 1913 reported that of its 57,210 circulation, 14,610 was outside the city. The paper had carried strips in 1908 but apparently dropped them in response to a national 'decency' campaign. See Elsa Nystrom, 'A Rejection of Order: The Development of the Newspaper Comic Strip in America, 1830-1920', PhD diss., Loyola University of Chicago, 1989, ch. 5 for a discussion of this campaign.
- 18 Harvey Lehman and Paul Witty's 1924 study revealed that reading comic strips was 'the one activity most frequently engaged in by children [of both sexes] during all seasons of the year, and Negro and white children alike manifested an inordinate interest in it'. 'The Compensatory Function of the Sunday Funny Paper', *Journal of Applied Psychology*, June 1927, p. 204.
- 19 William Taylor, 'The Launching of Commercial Culture: New York City, 1860-1939', in John Hull Mollenkopf (ed.), *Power, Culture, and Place: Essays on New York City*, Russell Sage Foundation, New York, 1988, p. 122.
- 20 For the decision limiting Outcault's copyright of the Yellow Kid to the character's name, see, W.B. Howell, Assistant Secretary, Treasury Department to W.Y. Connor, *New York Journal*, 15 April 1897, reprinted in *Decisions of the United States Courts involving Copyright and Literary Property, 1789-1909, Bulletin 15*, Library of Congress, Washington, D.C., 1980, pp. 3187-88. Artists developed the naughty kid theme mostly in urban settings, although occasionally they used rural themes. Mark Twain's Tom Sawyer and Huckleberry Finn demonstrate that the Victorian icon of the innocent child always had strong competition from mischievous non-urban types.
- 21 Maud Summers, *Editor and Publisher*, vol. 19, September 1908, p. 3, cited in Nystrom, 'A Rejection of Order', p. 172; and 'The Comic Nuisance', *Outlook*, vol. 91, 6 March 1909, p. 528. Buster Brown was also praised by Norman Hapgood, editor of *Collier's Weekly*, at a New York meeting of the League for the Improvement of the Children's Comic Supplement, see 'Make Comics Educational', *Survey*, vol. 26, 15 April 1911, p. 103. 'Buster Brown and The Bull', *New York Herald*, 14 May 1905.
- 22 The basis of the decision in favour of the *Herald* was that it was the paper that had copyrighted the title of the comic strip 'Buster Brown' by publishing the strip. See *New York Herald Co. v Star Co.* (146 Federal Reporter 204), *Outcault et al. v New York Herald* (146 Federal Reporter 205), and (146 Federal Reporter 1023) for the Circuit Court of Appeal decision upholding the lower court verdict. In *Outcault et al. v Lamar* (119 New York Supplement 930) the New York Supreme Court Appellate Division found that Outcault had retained all other rights to Buster Brown in an agreement with the *Herald* of 1 October 1902. See *Outcault et al. v Bonheur* (104 New York Supplement 1099) for details of Outcault's earnings from the stage show. Around this time Buster declared, 'Yes you can find *justice* in the dictionary, not in the court house'. (*New York American*, 4 October 1908.) A readership of 2.5 people per copy of a newspaper would give the papers carrying 'Buster Brown' a coverage of 10.3 per cent of the population according to the 1900 census and 8.5 per cent by the 1910 census. In 1908 the five largest cities in America, New York, Chicago, Philadelphia, St. Louis, and Boston, made up 55.9 per cent of the potential audience for comic strips. Hearst's version of 'Buster Brown' was published in New York, Chicago, and Boston that together accounted for 43 per cent of the total comic strip audience. Smaller centres accounted for the rest of the potential audience that received Hearst's 'Buster Brown'. The *Herald's* version added three locations to the audience for 'Buster Brown': St Louis, which represented 3.9 per cent of the potential audience, and Des Moines and Wheeling, which between them represented .5 per cent of that audience. Buster's audience then was mostly in large urban centres but with a significant percentage

- in rural regional centres. 'Buster Brown' was carried by newspapers in cities and towns with a total population of 11,432,359. Of this 1,573,571, or 13.76 per cent, resided outside the five major cities.
- 23 For a discussion of these other visual trademarks see Susan Strasser, *Satisfaction Guaranteed: The Making of the American Mass Market*, Pantheon Books, New York, 1989, pp. 182-183; and Stephen R. Fox, *The Mirror Makers: A History of American Advertising and Its Creators*, Morrow, New York, 1984, pp. 46-7.
 - 24 Robert Lesser, *A Celebration of Comic Art and Memorabilia*, Hawthorn Books, New York, 1975, p. 120.
 - 25 Author's telephone conversation with Frances Charman (a former employee of Buster Brown Textiles Incorporated), 11 November 1991. Unfortunately the company disposed of most of its early records in the 1950s. The Frank pamphlet, *Some Frank Con-fess-ions of Buster Brown*, is held Warshaw Collection of Business Americana, NMAH-AC 60, Shoes, box 9.
 - 26 The 1902 advertisement mentioned four plants. The Brown Shoe Co. catalogue No. 31, c. 1907, contains an illustration of the company's eight plants. Both items held Warshaw Collection, NMAH-AC 60, Shoes, box 9. J.H. Sawyer, 'Buster Brown Advertises Shoes', *Judicious Advertising*, vol. 8, March, 1910, pp. 27-30, 89.
 - 27 Reading comic strips itself required an act of consumption — the purchase of a newspaper.
 - 28 'Ah Well, Boys Will Be Boys', *New York American*, 19 April 1914.
 - 29 The Seattle advertisement is reprinted in Richard F. Outcault, *Buster Brown* [The Hyperion Library of Classic American Comic Strips], Hyperion, Westport, Conn., 1977. Nystrom cites the same resolution in an advertisement in the *Los Angeles Times*, 19 March 1911 (p. 128, fn. 28).
 - 30 'A Visit to Papa's Office', *New York American*, 22 April 1906.
 - 31 Providence *Journal*, 7 December 1913. Outcault also included outright plugs for 'Buster Brown' products into the comic strip. In 1903 one episode contained a sign in the background advising, 'Try a Buster Brown Mixture For Colds' ('Buster Brown at the Soda Water Fountain', *New York Herald*, 31 May 1903). The 6 May 1906 strip, 'How to Tame a Lion', in the *New York American* had a man in a lion suit asking Buster 'Hello Old Chap. Don't you remember — I used to play Tige in your show'. A reference to the Buster Brown stage show. Outcault also poked fun at the range of 'Buster Brown' products in a 17 December 1905 episode. But even this episode can be read as a plug for Buster's trademark, especially with its resolution extolling the joys of giving.
 - 32 The original graphics for the copyrighted advertisements are now held by the Library's Prints and Photographs Division. Unfortunately they have not been organised since being transferred from the Copyright Office and are not available for consultation. These two sides to Buster's character probably account for the different interpretations of the strip by Maud Summers and the *Outlook* editorial writer.
 - 33 Hal Barron, 'With All The Fragrant Powders of the Merchant: Mail-Order Buying in the Rural North, 1870-1920', unpublished paper in author's possession.
 - 34 See Jane Gaines, *Contested Culture: The Image, the Voice, and the Law*, University of North Carolina Press, Chapel Hill, 1991, for an account of intellectual property law and culture.